

Dendrochronological analysis of timber from a mill at Favrholt Mølle, near Hillerød, Denmark.

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Commissioned by Klaus Hvid, Museum Nordsjælland – Hillerød.

Thirty samples from a mill structure found during excavations at Favrholt Mølle near Hillerød were submitted for dendrochronological and wood anatomical analysis. A total of 28 samples were found suitable for dendrochronological dating and of these 26 could be dated. (The two samples of oak that could not be dated contain just 46 and 56 tree-rings, respectively.) The majority of the material is of *Quercus sp.*, oak but two timbers are of *Fagus sp.*, beech.

Fig. 1. Favrholt mølle. Diagram showing the chronological position of the tree-ring curves from the timbers from the mill.

		B0370069	B0370089	B0370029	B037003a	B037012a	B0370179	B037004a	B0370059	B0370139	B0370169	B0370199	B037001a	B0370109	B0370079	B0370119	B0370159	B0370279	B0370189	B037021a	B0370239	B0370209	B0370269	B0370229	B037025a	B037029b	B0370308	
Average B037M001		*	3,59	4,53	3,66	-	3,35	5,46	4,21	5,26	3,53	3,82	3,91	4,76	5,94	4,53	5,09	4,91	4,05	3,08	-	3,66	-	3,94	4,65	-	-	
		3,59	*	3,34	4,07	-	4,07	-	4,99	4,49	6,73	4,43	3,84	6,1	3,59	3,44	4,74	4,24	4,57	4,08	-	5,28	4,21	4,85	-	-	-	
		4,53	3,34	*	6,54	4,9	4,58	6,22	5,25	6,66	6,15	4,78	5,31	5,16	6,07	6,98	4,88	4,82	5,79	4,43	-	3,54	5,54	3,57	3,84	-	-	
		3,66	4,07	6,54	*	6,91	7,56	6,18	5,97	5,93	7,21	5,92	3,17	5,96	5,52	5,3	5,98	5,61	6,42	5,97	4,77	4,12	4,64	5,36	4,39	-	-	
		-	-	4,9	6,91	*	8,09	6,43	5,97	5,05	5,6	5,13	4,42	4,43	6,72	5,99	7,07	4,99	7,46	3,38	3,37	5,04	5,66	4,91	-	-	-	
		3,35	4,07	4,58	7,56	8,09	*	5,36	4,52	5,3	5,61	6,65	4,52	5,48	6,65	7,18	5,41	4,9	6,19	-	4,43	5,59	5,27	3,04	-	-	-	
		5,46	-	6,22	6,18	6,43	5,36	*	6,98	7,76	8,32	6,04	4,84	4,23	7,86	7,18	4,19	4,77	4,79	6,31	6,28	3,28	-	5,25	-	-	-	
		4,21	4,99	5,25	5,97	5,97	4,52	6,98	*	7,49	9,67	6,39	4,54	7,5	7,54	7,04	4,91	6,23	6,42	6,49	3,22	4,14	4,79	3,69	-	-	-	
		5,26	4,49	6,66	5,93	5,05	5,3	7,76	7,49	*	12,9	6	5,16	5,2	5,34	4,34	4,64	-	6,48	7,19	-	-	-	5,06	3,05	-	-	
		3,53	6,73	6,15	7,21	5,6	5,61	8,32	9,67	12,9	*	10,52	7,41	7,47	6,46	7,38	4,52	7,9	7,52	6,29	3,62	3,85	3,45	4,7	-	-	-	
	ST1		3,82	4,43	4,78	5,92	5,13	6,65	6,04	6,39	6	10,52	*	7,68	4,89	7,16	6,45	3,33	6,49	6,91	6,07	6,66	3,59	3,42	3,77	-	-	-
		3,91	3,84	5,31	3,17	4,42	4,52	4,84	4,54	5,16	7,41	7,68	*	7,16	8,03	6,67	7,24	3,94	5,04	4,23	3,91	3,86	3,35	-	-	-	-	
		4,76	6,1	5,16	5,96	4,43	5,48	4,23	7,5	5,2	7,47	4,89	7,16	*	6,99	6,98	6,23	8,75	5,29	3,13	-	4,71	4,81	4,14	4,5	-	-	
	ST2		5,94	3,59	6,07	5,52	6,72	6,65	7,86	7,54	5,34	6,46	7,16	8,03	6,99	*	15,73	12,28	10,11	6,64	3,84	3,54	5,45	5,61	-	3,37	-	
		4,53	3,44	6,98	5,3	5,99	7,18	7,18	7,04	4,34	7,38	6,45	6,67	6,98	15,73	*	10,43	9,32	5,9	3,25	3,25	4,51	4,27	-	3,22	-	-	
		5,09	4,74	4,88	5,98	7,07	5,41	4,19	4,91	4,64	4,52	3,33	7,24	6,23	12,28	10,43	*	7,11	6,61	3,32	3,01	6,2	6,1	3,46	3,96	-	-	
		4,91	4,24	4,82	5,61	4,99	4,9	4,77	6,23	-	7,9	6,49	3,94	8,75	10,11	9,32	7,11	*	5,23	4,87	-	4,03	3,37	-	4,45	-	-	
		4,05	4,57	5,79	6,42	7,46	6,19	4,79	6,42	6,48	7,52	6,91	5,04	5,29	6,64	5,9	6,61	5,23	*	4,8	3,65	4,51	5,22	-	-	-	-	
		3,08	4,08	4,43	5,97	3,38	-	6,31	6,49	7,19	6,29	6,07	4,23	3,13	3,84	3,25	3,32	4,87	4,8	*	4,95	-	-	4,25	3,94	-	-	
		-	-	-	4,77	3,37	4,43	6,28	3,22	-	3,62	6,66	3,91	-	3,54	3,25	3,01	-	3,65	4,95	*	4,01	-	5,03	-	-	-	
	3,66	5,28	3,54	4,12	5,04	5,59	3,28	4,14	-	3,85	3,59	3,86	4,71	5,45	4,51	6,2	4,03	4,51	-	4,01	*	3,36	4,94	-	-	-		
	-	4,21	5,54	4,64	5,66	5,27	-	4,79	-	3,45	3,42	3,35	4,81	5,61	4,27	6,1	3,37	5,22	-	-	3,36	*	4,78	-	-	-		
	3,94	4,85	3,57	5,36	4,91	3,04	5,25	3,69	5,06	4,7	3,77	-	4,14	-	-	3,46	-	-	4,25	5,03	4,94	4,78	*	-	-	-		
bøg		4,65	-	3,84	4,39	-	-	-	-	3,05	-	-	-	4,5	3,37	3,22	3,96	4,45	-	3,94	-	-	-	-	*	-		
		-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	*	3,03		
		-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	3,03	*	

Table 1. Favrholt mølge. Table showing the correlation (t-test) between each tree-ring curve with each other, at their cross-dated position.

The analysis suggests a very homogeneous timber material. The tree-ring curves from the samples achieve significant correlation with each other.

Tree 1

The tree-ring curves from two of the samples (B0370139 dp13 A28 and B0370169 dp16 A48) are so similar (see table 1) they might have been made from the same tree. They are highlighted in fig. 1 using blue. The two tree-ring curves are averaged to form one, to represent that tree.

Tree 2

The tree-ring curves from three other samples (B0370079 dp7 A15, B0370119 dp11 A22 and B0370159 dp15 A47) are also so similar, that they might have been made from the same tree (table 1). These are highlighted with green in fig. 1. These three are averaged to one curve, to represent that tree.

Two of the samples analysed were identified as beech. They were two pieces with the same sample number and might have been taken from the same timber, but this cannot be confirmed. These two samples are dated. Sapwood cannot be identified on beech and no bark edge was observed on these. The outermost preserved

complete ring is on sample vp3 (B037029b) which was formed in AD 1512. The beech trees were felled after AD 1513.

Of the 24 dated oak samples 18 have sapwood preserved. Of these, five have complete sapwood to bark edge preserved. The last ring formed on sample dp2 was fully formed, so the tree that the sample comes from was felled in winter AD 1547-48. The outermost ring on two other samples (dp20 and vp4) was not fully formed. These two are from trees felled in spring/summer AD 1548. Samples dp12 and dp22 are from trees felled in winter AD 1550-51.

Given the homogeneity of the material and the possibility that single trees are used at different positions throughout the structure suggests that the mill was built in one process, of timbers felled in the same region over a few years. There is no evidence in the dendrochronological analysis for repair of the structure.

FileNames	-	-	B037M001	B037025a	
-	start	dates	AD1337	AD1417	
-	dates	end	AD1550	AD1531	
<i>Swedish chronologies</i>					
SM000005	AD1274	AD1974	7,78	4,75	Skåne Blekinge [Lund University]
LS10MM01	AD1391	AD1490	6,80	4,72	Maria church Sweden 6 timbers (Lund Uni revised Daly 2007)
O0800009	AD1301	AD1561	6,72	3,26	Halmstad Sweden (Bartholin pers comm)
LS10BM01	AD1413	AD1509	6,70	5,16	Löddeköp Torn Sweden 2 timbers (Lund Uni revised Daly 2007)
<i>Danish chronologies</i>					
F012M001	AD1456	AD1574	7,59	3,73	Gl. Estrup voldgrav 2 trees (Daly unpubl)
<i>Chronologies containing timber probably imported</i>					
CD839Z01	AD1366	AD1511	11,09	3,39	Sulsted kirke 4 timbers [Nationalmuseet revised Daly 2007]
B028M003	AD1386	AD1576	10,58	6,44	Køge Havn 4 timbers (Daly 2013)
EP31539	AD1361	AD1539	9,99	5,30	Stirling Castle Scotland Ep3 1539 imports 15 timbers (Crone pers comm)
2121M002	AD1052	AD1596	9,24	5,92	Suså Næstved all posts [Daly 2001b]
B027oak B	AD1248	AD1532	8,83	5,01	Gammel Strand Copenhagen purple 21 timbers [Daly 2016b]
ZEALAND	AD452	AD1770	8,82	5,63	Sjælland Denmark 249 timbers [Daly unpubl]
CD40UZ02	AD1372	AD1519	8,18	3,01	Brogade 4 timbers [Nationalmuseet revised Daly 2007]
q415029m0	AD1356	AD1540	8,15	5,41	Evangelistas altarpiece Seville Cathedral 29 planks [Rodríguez-Trobajo & Domínguez-Delmás 2015]
4077M00X	AD1178	AD1546	7,93	5,72	Nyborg slot gruppe A og B 46 timbers [Daly 1999]
8111M001	AD1350	AD1480	7,85	3,96	Astrup K. 13 timbers [Daly 1998a]
B027oak C	AD1331	AD1557	7,82	7,35	Gammel Strand Copenhagen orange 23 timbers [Daly 2016b]
8127M001	AD846	AD1771	7,60	7,42	Ålborg Østerå + Boulevarden 67 timbers [Daly 2000 2001a]
H11K2M01	AD1401	AD1545	7,54	4,32	Lübeck Koenigstr 4 timbers (Hamburg Uni revised Daly 2007)
D014M001	AD1319	AD1521	7,27	3,40	Nørregade Gråbrødre klostres baghave 2 timbers (Daly 2015a)
81M00004	AD1350	AD1480	6,69	3,65	kirker i Vendsyssel W Sweden group 24 timber [Daly 1998b]
<i>Chronologies from ships</i>					
00652M02	AD1405	AD1607	8,79	6,95	Copenhagen B&W Grund Ship 2. 2 trees [Daly 1997]
Z141M001	AD1394	AD1529	8,45	4,73	Klippan 2 ship Västergötland 11 timbers trimmed (Daly 2015b)
Z147M002	AD1363	AD1535	7,01	5,54	Bispevika 4 ship Oslo B3B7 5 timbers [Daly 2016a]

Table 2. Favrholm mølle. Result of the correlation between the average curve from the timbers and a single curve and diverse Northern European site and master chronologies. The source of the chronologies is given. The grey tone highlights the high *t*-values.

As mentioned above, the correlation between the tree-ring curves from the oak samples indicates a very homogeneous timber material (table 1). An average of the tree-ring curves from all but one of the oaks has been made (B037M001), representing 20 trees. The average is 214 years in length, covering the period AD 1337-1550. The oak material is dating using a wide range of oak tree-ring datasets for Northern Europe but the highest correlation (t-test) is achieved with southern Scandinavian chronologies. Many of these chronologies consist of imported timber, as by the 16th century extensive timber transport was taking place for building. For example, Stirling Castle in Scotland was built using Southern Scandinavian oak, and two 16th century harbour bulwarks at Gammel Strand seem to be of west Swedish oak. That the oak material from Favrholt Mølle achieves highest correlation with many of the site chronologies shown to be of west Swedish provenance suggests that this material was imported from there.

To estimate the felling date of the oaks a sapwood statistic for Northern Germany has been used. Oaks here have, on average, 20 (-5 +10) sapwood years (Hollstein 1980)). For measuring and for the analysis and the calculation of the *t*-value ("t-test"), "DENDRO" (Tyers, 1997) and "CROS" (Baillie & Pilcher, 1973) are used. In the analysis master and site chronologies for Northern Europe are employed.

Literature

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Catalogue

Filename	sample title and number	rings	start yr.	end yr.	pith	sapwood	bark?	Conversion	extra end	Ave. ring width mm	Interpretation / felling
<i>Samples</i>											
B037001a	MNS 50035 Favrholt Mølle dp1 A3 QUSP	151	AD1368	AD1518	C	0	N	H	H1	0,88	after AD1534
B0370029	MNS 50035 Favrholt Mølle dp2 A5 QUSP	162	AD1386	AD1547	C	17	W	H	N	0,94	AD1547 winter
B037003a	MNS 50035 Favrholt Mølle dp3 A6 QUSP	151	AD1389	AD1539	C	8	N	S	S1	1,28	AD1546-61
B037004a	MNS 50035 Favrholt Mølle dp4 A9 QUSP	166	AD1378	AD1543	F	15	N	H	S1	1,40	AD1544-58
B0370059	MNS 50035 Favrholt Mølle dp5 A12 QUSP	115	AD1406	AD1520	C	0	N	S	H1	1,34	after AD1536
B0370069	MNS 50035 Favrholt Mølle dp6 A14 QUSP	123	AD1407	AD1529	F	0	?	?	S1	1,45	AD1544-59
B0370079	MNS 50035 Favrholt Mølle dp7 A15 QUSP	154	AD1381	AD1534	C	10	N	S	S1	0,95	AD1543-58
B0370089	MNS 50035 Favrholt Mølle dp8 A17 QUSP	124	AD1418	AD1541	C	8	N	S	S1	1,36	AD1548-63
	MNS 50035 Favrholt Mølle dp9 A18										NOT DELIVERED
B0370109	MNS 50035 Favrholt Mølle dp10 A21 QUSP	149	AD1396	AD1544	C	25	N	H	S1	0,99	AD1545-9
B0370119	MNS 50035 Favrholt Mølle dp11 A22 QUSP	165	AD1375	AD1539	C	11	N	O	S1	0,86	AD1543-58
B037012a	MNS 50035 Favrholt Mølle dp12 A27 QUSP	150	AD1401	AD1550	F	17	W	H	N	1,02	AD1550 winter
B0370139	MNS 50035 Favrholt Mølle dp13 A28 QUSP	183	AD1337	AD1519	C	0	N	S	H1	1,17	after AD1539
B037014a	MNS 50035 Favrholt Mølle dp14 A36 QUSP	46			C	0	N	R	H1	2,80	Not dated
B0370159	MNS 50035 Favrholt Mølle dp15 A47 QUSP	145	AD1395	AD1539	C	12	N	H	S1	1,05	AD1543-58
B0370169	MNS 50035 Favrholt Mølle dp16 A48 QUSP	128	AD1396	AD1523	C	0	N	H	H1	1,35	after AD1539
B0370179	MNS 50035 Favrholt Mølle dp17 A49 QUSP	157	AD1381	AD1537	C	6	N	S	S1	0,99	AD1546-61
B0370189	MNS 50035 Favrholt Mølle dp18 A50 QUSP	188	AD1344	AD1531	C	2	N	T	N	0,99	AD1544-59
B0370199	MNS 50035 Favrholt Mølle dp19 A51 QUSP	139	AD1374	AD1512	C	0	B	S	S1	1,26	AD1527-42
B0370209	MNS 50035 Favrholt Mølle dp20 A52 QUSP	129	AD1419	AD1547	C	20	X	H	N	1,48	AD1548 spring/summer
B037021a	Favrholt Mølle MNS 50035 DP21 A53 QUSP	137	AD1390	AD1526	C	10	N	?	S1	1,21	AD1531-46
B0370229	MNS 50035 Favrholt Mølle dp22 A59 QUSP	167	AD1384	AD1550	C	22	W	H	N	1,26	AD1550 winter
B0370239	MNS 50035 Favrholt Mølle dp23 A60 QUSP	159	AD1365	AD1523	C	2	N	H	S1	1,32	AD1536-51
B037024a	MNS 50035 Favrholt Mølle dp24 A61 QUSP	56			C	8	N	O	S1	3,03	Not dated
B037025a	MNS 50035 Favrholt Mølle vp1 A16 QUSP	115	AD1417	AD1531	C	0	N	O	H1	1,10	after AD1547
B0370269	MNS 50035 Favrholt Mølle dp26 A25 QUSP	147	AD1399	AD1545	C	15	N	S	S1	1,05	AD1546-60
B0370279	MNS 50035 Favrholt Mølle vp4 A81 QUSP	167	AD1381	AD1547	C	25	X	S	N	0,93	AD1548 spring/summer
B037029b	MNS 50035 Favrholt Mølle vp3 A56 FASY	90	AD1423	AD1512	F	0	N	T	H1	2,05	after AD1513
B0370308	MNS 50035 Favrholt Mølle vp3 A56 FASY	93	AD1390	AD1482	C	0	N	T	H1	3,01	after AD1483
	MNS 50035 Favrholt Mølle vp2 A31 QUSP	60						T			NOT ANALYSED
	MNS 50035 Favrholt Mølle vp4 A81 QUSP										Mill paddle?
<i>Same tree</i>											
B037st01	MNS 50035 Favrholt Mølle same tree 13 16 QUSP	187	AD1337	AD1523	C	0	N		N	1,20	after AD1539
B037st02	MNS 50035 Favrholt Mølle same tree 7 11 15 QUSP	165	AD1375	AD1539	C	11	N		N	0,97	AD1543-58
<i>Average</i>											
B037M001	MNS 50035 Favrholt Mølle 20 timbers QUSP	214	AD1337	AD1550						1,17	
B037029&30 beech	MNS 50035 Favrholt Mølle 29&30 beech 2 timbers FASY	123	AD1390	AD1512						2,49	
Conversion: R = radial split plank, T = tangential plank, W = whole timber, S = squared whole timber, H = half timber, Q = quarter timber, O = other conversion. Pith: C = centre, V = less than 5 rings, F = 5 - 10 rings, G = greater than 10 rings.											
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in publication bibliography/literature lists:	Daly, Aoife, 2016. Dendrochronological analysis of timber from a mill at Favrholt Mølle, near Hillerød, Denmark. <i>dendro.dk report 2016:47</i> , Copenhagen.
In blogs and social media:	<i>dendro.dk report 2016:47</i>